

CrisPR/CRIS systems are highly effective and useful for genomic manipulation. Despite this, cardiac treatment remains difficult due to existing genome editing and delivery processes

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Abstract- CRISPR/Cas9 systems, in particular, have emerged as an important and promising technology for in vitro and in vivo genomic manipulation. Although genome editing has been used in the cardiovascular community as a scientific tool to study disease pathogenesis, therapeutic genome editing has yet to be used in clinical practice. PCSK9 is one of the most promising therapeutic genome editing candidates in the liver, and it has been thoroughly studied for cardiovascular disease risk reduction. Despite this, owing to the inefficiency of current genome editing technologies and distribution systems in the heart, treating the heart remains challenging. We should expect a steady stream of new editing approaches targeting wider use, given that clinical genome editing is still in its early stages but is rapidly progressing. It would be necessary to develop safe and reliable distribution systems in order to use such creative approaches in clinical settings

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the most significant developments in biology in the last decade has been the advancement of genome editing technology, which has revolutionized biomedical research (1-4). Modern genome editing techniques have made it even simpler and quicker to change genomic DNA sequences inside the genomes of living organisms than approaches using traditional homologous recombination, which can also adjust genomic sequences and are widely used to produce genetic models. Basically, genome editing methods use programmable nucleases type zinc finger nucleases (ZFNs) (5), transcription activator-like effector nucleases (TALENs) (6,7), and clustered frequently interspaced short palindromic repeats (CRISPR)/CRISPR-associated 9 (Cas9) nucleases to harness the endogenous repair mechanism of DNA double-strand breaks (DSBs). The application of the CRISPR/Cas9 method to eukaryotic genome editing (8), which was first discovered as a part of the immune system within bacteria, was a crucial initial technical advance. CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing methods have been widely used in numerous scientific fields due to their simplicity and performance (8).

Genome editing technology can be used in biomedical science in two ways (2-4). One possibility is to use genome editing as a scientific method to learn more about biological processes and disease pathophysiology. The other choice is to use genome editing as a clinical method for treating or preventing diseases (1, 9-11).

For starters, genome editing technology has been used in a number of studies (2-4). It sped up the development of genetic animal models and cellular models, including knockout and knock-in mouse models, for example. Traditional approaches for producing knockout mice include homologous recombination in mouse embryonic stem cells (ESCs), colony selection in ESCs, injection of transformed ESCs into mouse embryos, and chimeric mouse breeding. Obtaining knockout mice is a lengthy procedure that can take months or years. CRISPR/Cas9 genome editors, on the other hand, may be inserted directly into single-cell mouse embryos to disrupt a gene, yielding knockout mice in a matter of weeks (12,13). Furthermore, CRISPR/Cas9 tools allow the development of genetic models of other animals, including nonhuman primates, which was previously impossible (14-16). Isogenic cell lines originating from patient-derived induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) are another example (17-23). Human iPSCs are an appealing forum for studying genetic disorders since they can be segregated to any desired cell type in general and can imitate the genetics of the patients of origin. Patient-derived iPSCs have been shown to recapitulate disease phenotypes on a dish in a variety of studies (24-48). Unlike model organisms like mice and rodents, however, patient-derived iPSCs have a diverse genetic history. The method of generating iPSCs from patients' somatic cells causes differences in epigenetics, pluripotency, and differentiation capability among iPSC lines (49). As a result, a direct comparison of illness and stable iPSCs may not be the best way to investigate the effect

of a certain genetic locus on disease phenotypes. To avoid the problems posed by genetic differences in iPSCs, it would be desirable to create isogenic iPSC lines that differ only at the locus of interest from the initial line. Other examples include the development of reporter cell lines, genetic locus imaging, impartial pooled genetic sequencing, in vivo lineage tracing, and so on. (4, 50-53).

Second, the advancement of genome editing technologies opens the door to therapeutic genome editing in diseased cells or tissues, with the aim of removing or correcting dangerous mutations or introducing beneficial changes to patients' genomes (1-11). Rare monogenic diseases and modern diseases are also candidates for therapeutic genome editing. Pathogenic mutations in disease-causing genes (e.g., F9 for hemophilia, HBB for sickle cell disease, and dystrophin for DMD) will need to be deleted or reversed by gene knockout or knock-in to cure monogenic diseases like hemophilia, sickle cell disease, and Duchenne muscular dystrophy (DMD). Beneficial mutations or preventive modifications of non-causal genes of diseases such as dyslipidemia and HIV infection will be added to cure emerging multifactorial diseases including dyslipidemia and HIV infection (e.g., PCSK9 for dyslipidemia, and CCR5 for HIV). In theory, CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing for patients can take many forms, including in vivo genome editing, ex vivo genome editing, and germline genome editing (1,4,9). However, gene editing of germline cells or embryos raises significant ethical concerns about heritability, including the fact that it would be an effective treatment for serious congenital diseases (1,54). In vivo and ex vivo genome editing of somatic cells are more ethically viable options. Ex vivo genome editing and re-implanting is a more convenient method of delivering genome editing to patients than in vivo genome editing. Since ex vivo culture of blood cells is similar to in vitro cell culture, and gene transmission to blood cells is simpler than delivery to solid tissues, this technique has been tested in particular in blood cells. Hematopoietic stem cells (HSCs) are harvested from a patient, modified, and then re-engrafted to the patient of origin because HSCs can live outside of the body and return to the bone marrow following transplantation in ex vivo editing therapy of blood cells (1,55). Clinical trials of therapeutic genome editing using CRISPR/Cas9 tools are currently in phase I for a few diseases. Ex vivo genome editing for-thalassemia and sickle cell disease using *Streptococcus pyogenes* Cas9 (SpCas9) is the first case (56). Another example is in vivo genome editing in the retina using *Staphylococcus aureus* Cas9 (SaCas9) transmitted by adeno-associated virus (AAV) for Type 10 Leber congenital amaurosis (57). Furthermore, multiple clinical trials of CAR-T therapy paired with ex vivo CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing (e.g., knockout of checkpoint inhibitor PD-1) are currently ongoing (58).

Genome editing techniques have been used in the cardiovascular area as both a research tool and a clinical tool, but mostly as a research tool (9,10). Various models have been developed to research the pathophysiology of genetic disorders. Patient-derived iPSCs and their isogenic control lines, for example, have been used to research familial hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (HCM), familial dilated cardiomyopathy (DCM), long QT syndrome (LQTS), laminopathy, and other conditions (26,29,32,34,35,37,38,41,42,44-48). Cardiomyopathy, hypertension, electrophysiology, and dyslipidemia models (59-63) are only a few examples of genetic animal models generated using genome editing techniques. Therapeutic genome editing studies in the cardiovascular area, on the other hand, have largely focused on the liver, especially those targeting Proprotein convertase subtilisin-kexin type 9 (PCSK9) for dyslipidemia (64-69). Despite the fact that certain cardiac disorders could theoretically be reversed by editing disease-causing genes, as shown in iPSC disease modeling experiments, targeting the heart is still difficult, even in laboratory models. The emphasis of this analysis is on therapeutic genome editing in the cardiovascular field, specifically using CRISPR/Cas9-based techniques (64-69).

II. CARDIOVASCULAR DISORDERS THAT MAY BE TARGETED BY GENOME EDITING

Genome editing may be used to cure or prevent two forms of cardiovascular disorders (1,9). The first type is affected by genetic regions in the heart or arteries that are responsible for the disease. This category includes a wide range of hereditary and acquired genetic diseases in cardiovascular tissues. HCM, DCM, LQTS, and muscular dystrophies that induce cardiac dysfunction are examples of this form of heart disease. Marfan syndrome and familial pulmonary hypertension are two examples of vascular disorders. While these diseases are potential therapeutic genome editing candidates in theory, existing genome editing technology makes it difficult to target primary cardiovascular tissues due to the inefficiency of in vivo editing and the lack of effective delivery methods, which we will explore later. While germline editing could be more beneficial for these diseases than in vivo editing, it raises ethical concerns. Another category includes those who are linked to cardiovascular risk factors, including dyslipidemia. Non-cardiovascular tissues, such as the liver or blood cells, are targets of genome editing in this form of disease. Because of its feasibility, the liver is currently the organ that has been researched the most for therapeutic genome editing of cardiovascular diseases (64-71). An ex vivo technique for blood cells may be applied to immune cells to increase systemic inflammation and avoid atherosclerosis (72,73).

Gene editing molecular pathways and methods for treating or preventing diseases Non-homologous end-joining (NHEJ) and homology-directed repair (HDR) are two types of non-homologous end-joining (NHEJ) (HDR) ZFN, TALENs, CRISPR/Cas9, and other genome editing tools rely on endogenous DNA repair processes (1-74). When genome editors insert an initial DSB, the host cell triggers endogenous DNA repair pathways to repair the damage. Non-homologous end-joining (NHEJ) and homology-directed repair are the two major forms of repair processes (HDR). DSBs are restored by the NHEJ mechanism in the absence of a repair DNA template (74). Endogenous repair machinery specifically ligates the ends of DSBs in NHEJ. NHEJ, on the other hand, is vulnerable to errors and often results in spontaneous insertion/deletion (indel) mutations at the junction site. If an indel is found inside a gene's coding sequence, it may trigger a frameshift or a premature stop codon, leading to gene knockout. NHEJ is a common repair mechanism that occurs during the cell cycle in most mammalian cell types. As a result, NHEJ genome editing may be used to knock out genes in a variety of cell types (1-74). DSBs can be repaired using the

HDR method in the presence of a repair DNA template (74). About the fact that HDR happens at a lower frequency than NHEJ, it can result in specific modifications that can be described by an exogenously inserted repair prototype. The repair prototype may be single-stranded DNA oligonucleotides or double-stranded DNA oligonucleotides with homology arms flanking the insertion sequence, as in traditional homologous recombination approaches (ssODNs). Unlike NHEJ, HDR is only involved in the S and G2 phases of the cell cycle, and its performance varies depending on the cell type and condition. Thus, HDR can be used to trigger knock-in of a particular DNA sequence in dividing cells, but it is rarely used in non-dividing cells like cardiomyocytes, where it is frequently outcompeted by alternate repair pathways like NHEJ (1-4,74). There are three major techniques for altering genomic DNA sequences to prevent or cure disease based on these two key forms of repair processes: destruction of a gene, deletion of a particular genomic region, and modification of a gene (1-4,9). A gene's disruptionThe most straightforward approach to using genome editing to prevent or cure disease is to disrupt a gene that is unhealthy or whose suppression is beneficial. NHEJ may be used to cause disruption within a gene for this reason. Targeting PCSK9 to lower blood cholesterol levels is a promising example of this strategy. PCSK9-targeting therapies have been designed to reduce LDL cholesterol levels in patients with persistently elevated LDL cholesterol levels even on statins, based on the finding that loss-of-function mutations in PCSK9 were associated with 15–28 percent lower LDL cholesterol levels and 47–88 percent lower risk of coronary heart disease (75).

Monoclonal antibodies against PCSK9, which have recently been licensed and can reduce LDL cholesterol significantly when used alone or in combination with a statin, must be taken on a regular basis. Since loss-of-function mutations in PCSK9 do not cause any obvious phenotypes, permanent disruption of PCSK9 via genome editing will be a promising strategy. Several studies (64-69) show that mouse PCSK9 can be attacked by NHEJ-mediated disruption to reduce LDL cholesterol using CRISPR/Cas9 that is virally transmitted to the liver with high efficiency. A genetic region is deleted NHEJ-mediated genome editing with two guide RNAs (gRNAs) flanking the locus to be deleted may also result in the deletion of a particular genomic region. If a disease-causing mutation causes a frameshift, a premature stop codon, or an ectopic splicing site, deleting the genomic regions surrounding the mutation can restore the gene's protein function. The "exon skipping" technique for Duchenne muscular dystrophy (DMD) (76) is a clear example of this approach. One of the most common lethal genetic disorders is DMD, which is an X-linked recessive muscle wasting disorder (1:5000 male births). Dystrophin, a large cytoskeletal structural protein required for muscle membrane stabilization, is the gene responsible for DMD. The mutations are often exon deletions, which interrupt the dystrophin gene's reading frame and result in the complete loss of functional dystrophin expression. DMD patients are normally diagnosed in infancy, and irregular heart function is discovered in early adolescence. Heart disease or respiratory failure commonly kills patients in their twenties. Despite the fact that gene therapy is a potential treatment choice for DMD, gene delivery of intact dystrophin is difficult due to the large size of the dystrophin coding sequence. Fortunately, the exon-skipping technique against truncated dystrophin has been shown to repair the reading frame and recover much of the functional protein (76-78).

Exon skipping has been suggested as a treatment choice for 75 percent of DMD patients (76-78). The FDA has also approved oligonucleotide-mediated exon-skipping drugs for the most frequent form of DMD with exon 51 mutation. Since genome editing can potentially target any exon, irreversible exon-skipping via genome editing may be a potential treatment for extreme DMD patients. Exon skipping was shown to restore functional dystrophin protein in a mouse model by in vivo genome editing (79-85). CRISPR/Cas9 was delivered to the skeletal muscle of mdx mice with a premature stop codon in exon 23 using an AAV virus. Despite the fact that the editing efficiency in skeletal muscle was only 2–3%, they demonstrated functional recovery in muscle strength after genome editing. In a canine model, the same technique was seen to work (86).

The precise effectiveness of genome editing in the heart in these models, however, is still unknown. It remains to be seen if exon skipping via genome editing will prevent heart failure, which is the most common cause of death in DMD patients. Genetic modificationSince there are many genetic disorders in the cardiovascular field, HDR gene correction has a lot of promise for therapeutic genome editing (21). However, due to the low efficiency of HDR in non-dividing somatic cells, especially cardiomyocytes, it is currently difficult to extend this approach to in vivo models. So far, no in vivo studies in the cardiovascular area have been published using this method.Gene correction by HDR is currently primarily used in in vitro platforms where successfully edited cells can be filtered and amplified (1,4). The phenotypes of monogenic diseases can be saved after gene correction, according to studies using patient-derived iPSCs (87). This method can not be extended to in vivo genome editing because these disease-modeling experiments of iPSCs use genome editing in the stem cell stage and then pick up edited iPSC clones and differentiate them into cell types responsible for the disease (cardiomyocytes, endothelial cells, etc.). However, if gene correction can be performed with high efficiency in somatic cells and 3D organs, these studies indicate that gene correction may be a possible therapeutic alternative. Given the poor efficiency of HDR in current CRISPR/Cas9 technology, diseases in which even a small percentage of corrected cells can at least partially restore function or diseases that can be handled by ex vivo editing, whether in somatic cells or iPSCs, are viable targets.3.5. Newer CRISPR/Cas9-based tools and other techniquesAfter the invention of CRISPR/Cas9 systems, a growing range of novel CRISPR/Cas9-based methods have emerged, with applications in gene control, epigenome editing, genomic imaging, and other areas (50-52,88).

The laws of NHEJ or HDR are not followed by these non-traditional instruments. Several cases of possible biomedical uses are briefly summarized here.The homology-independent targeted integration (HITI) strategy (89) is one approach with potential for cardiac genome editing. Since HDR's gene correction technique is ineffective in non-dividing cells, this new method was created to accomplish gene correction

without the use of HDR. DNA knock-in is possible with HITI also in non-dividing cells. Since NHEJ is involved in both dividing and non-dividing cells, HITI uses modified NHEJ instead of HDR for gene correction. Importantly, using AAVs, this procedure was shown to be capable of knocking in a reporter gene into the mouse heart. SATI, a new approach created by the same community, was recently published (intercellular linearized Single homology Arm donor mediated intron-Targeting Integration). SATI is a hybrid of single homology arm-mediated HDR and HITI that allows for greater target versatility (90).

Base editors may be a good substitute for HDR-mediated gene correction (91-94). Since base editing uses cytidine deaminases rather than DSBs to recruit enzymes, it has the potential to boost efficiency while limiting DSB damage. The detailed translation of C to T has enormous therapeutic potential for point mutation repair. Although targetable mutations are constrained by the PAM sequences of base editing tools (93,94), it is estimated that 3000 genetic variants in ClinVar could be corrected by C > T substitution. Several research (95-97) have shown that base editors may be used to correct therapeutic genes in mouse models. However, similar to the NHEJ gene disruption technique, research into base-editing therapy for cardiovascular disorders has been restricted to PCSK9 in the liver, with no reports of base-editing in the heart (95). Despite the fact that there are several disorders that can be handled through C > T replacement (e.g., hereditary cardiomyopathy, congenital cardiac diseases, LQTS, etc.), delivering base editors to the heart is also difficult due to the fact that base editors are massive fusion proteins that surpass the packing capability of AAVs.

A strong new method known as "prime editing" was recently announced. It works by combining a Cas9 H840A nickase with a reverse transcriptase. The prime editing guide RNAs (pegRNAs) contain reverse-transcribed sequences that would be inserted to the intended locus, as well as sequences that would determine the target loci. Without DSBs or donor DNA templates, prime editing allows for targeted insertions, deletions, and all 12 possible base-to-base transformations. In theory, this new method could correct up to 89 percent of identified genetic variants associated with human diseases, making it a promising candidate for therapeutic genome editing (98).

CRISPR/Cas9-based gene regulation tools, in addition to genome editing tools, may be useful for therapeutic applications (52,88,99). CRISPR interference (CRISPRi) and CRISPR activation (CRISPRa) systems have been developed using nuclease-deactivated Cas9 to control gene expression rather than editing genomic DNA (dCas9). Since dCas9 retains its ability to bind gRNAs and targeted DNA but lacks nuclease function, it can be used to recruit protein and RNA factors to a specific DNA site without cleaving genomic DNA. For CRISPRi and CRISPRa, transcriptional repressors (e.g., KRAB) and activators (e.g., VP64) are fused to dCas9 to achieve gene repression and activation, respectively. Histone acetylation (e.g., H3K27Ac using p300) (100,101), histone demethylation (e.g., H3K9me3 using KRAB) (102), DNA methylation (using DNMT3A/L) (103,104), and DNA demethylation (using TET1) (105) have all been produced using dCas9 in addition to CRISPRi/a. In terms of biomedical applications, no trials of in vivo gene therapy using CRISPRi/a or other epigenome editors have been published to date. While a CRISPRi method may potentially be used to treat diseases that are targets for antibody drugs, CRISPRa could be more appealing because gene activation with current molecular selective therapy is difficult.

III. Obstacles in the way of clinical gene editing

3.1. Goal sequence versatility and flexibility

The flexibility of target sites is determined by how genome editors recognize the target location. Each genome editing tool binds to a different DNA chain. CRISPR/Cas9-based systems have a simpler and more versatile target-site selection rule than ZFN or TALEN-based systems. In a nutshell, CRISPR/Cas9 genome editors bind to a 20-bp protospacer sequence identified by a gRNA, which must be accompanied by a Protospacer Adjacent Motif (PAM) sequence. A PAM series is unique to each Cas9 variant. SpCas9 and SaCas9, for example, have PAM sequences of 5'-NGG and 5'-NNGRRT, respectively. The target site versatility is reduced for Cas9 variants with more complex PAM sequences. However, the increasing number of Cas9 models that are becoming available quickly will soon overcome this restriction (1-4, 9). Non-unique genomic sequences around the target sites may restrict their availability in certain cases. Designing suitable gRNAs to carry Cas9 to a target site that is within repeat sequences or has no adjacent sequences that are unusual relative to the rest of the genome can be challenging. As a result, genes in these locations will be poor candidates for genome editing treatment.

3.2. Editing performance on goal

It is important to achieve high editing efficiency at a desired genomic site in a desired tissue for therapeutic genome editing. Despite the development of a variety of new approaches to increase on-target editing performance, achieving highly effective in vivo editing in many types of solid tissues, including the heart (106,107), remains a challenge.

Since local chromatin structure and epigenetic status influence genome editor accessibility to the target site, editing efficiency varies across loci, cell cycle stages, cell types, and tissue types (106-110). For in vivo genome editing, the difference in editing efficiency across tissues is particularly significant. Several groups (64-69) succeeded in in vivo genome editing of PCSK9 in mouse liver through NHEJ-mediated gene disruption as a possible trigger of dyslipidemia. These experiments show that the editing performance in the mouse liver is sufficient to achieve the functional phenotype. CRISPR/Cas9 was delivered to the mouse liver using viral vectors, and more than half of the cells were knocked out, resulting in lower LDL cholesterol levels. In vivo genome editing in the heart, on the other hand, has a much lower performance (79-86,107). After systematic administration of viral vectors to postnatal mice, the efficiency in cardiomyocytes was just 2–10%. While the efficiency of

delivery systems affects genome editing, tissue (or cell) type appears to be another significant factor that influences genome editor operation. Except in a Cas9-transgenic mouse model, where distribution of the big Cas9 protein would not be a challenge, editing performance in the heart was still poor (60). Another interesting finding was that when genome editing was done in neonatal mice, the editing quality of the heart was higher (79,83). When AAV8 was systemically administered to neonatal (P2) mdx mice, approximately 9% of gene alteration was observed in the heart up to one year after genome editing (83). The variations in editing performance between the liver and the heart, as well as between the neonatal and adult heart, are most likely due to differences in epigenetic status, such as chromatin accessibility, DNA repair machinery function, and cell cycle phases. In the cardiovascular region, genome editing in the liver has been studied more thoroughly than genome editing in the heart due to the adult heart's poor editing ability. Currently, using NHEJ to reduce the risk of atherosclerosis in the liver is a more viable approach than using it to treat inherited cardiac conditions in the heart.

While there are many genetic disorders for which gene repair of the heart might theoretically be a possible therapeutic alternative (e.g., HCM, DCM, LQTS, etc.) in the cardiovascular area, the heart's poor editing efficiency will be a major barrier (9-11). HDR-mediated gene repair is far more difficult than NHEJ-mediated gene destruction or deletion, as discussed previously. Methods to increase the efficacy of HDR must be built in order to realize *in vivo* genome editing of the heart as a cure for inherited heart disorders. Inhibiting NHEJ, activating HDR, or modifying cell cycle status are all possible options (106, 111-114). Another strategy is to create gene correction methods that do not rely on HDR, such as HITI or prime editing (89,98).

3.3 Off-target mutagenesis

While genome editing's on-target performance has increased, the most important problem in realizing the promise of genome-editing therapy is protection (115). In addition to the dangers associated with other gene therapy (e.g., transmission reagent toxicity, immune response, etc.), all forms of therapeutic genome editing carry the risk of off-target mutagenesis, which occurs when new mutations are added to sites in the genome other than the targeted on-target location. Off-target mutations in target cells or tissues may trigger unwanted functional phenotypes like oncogenesis (1-4). Off-target mutagenesis makes treating the heart more difficult than other tissues in the cardiovascular region, so even uncommon off-target mutations can induce cardiac arrhythmias that can be lethal to the patient.

Off-target mutations vary between people because each patient has a particular genetic history that can not be replicated using model organisms (1,116,117). As a result, prior to therapeutic implementation, each patient's off-target mutations must be assessed. Off-target mutations should be checked before *ex vivo* genome editing cells or tissues are implanted into the original patients. However, assessing off-target results prior to *in vivo* genome editing will be more difficult. Patients' primary cells or iPSC-derived cells may be used to monitor genome editing and anticipate off-target results in patients (1,116,117).

A variety of methods for detecting off-target mutations have been developed, but they are still in the early stages of development, and no systematic methods for therapeutic genome editing in patients have been developed (118). Off-target mutations can be assessed using three different methods of assays. To begin, numerous *in silico* methods for predicting off-target sites have been developed and are now widely used in gRNA design. These tools are focused on the idea that a locus's off-target potential is determined by how close its sequence is to the on-target site (115,119,120). Despite the fact that these methods are useful and commonly used due to their ease, recent studies have shown that off-target editing can occur at locations other than those expected by sequence similarity. Second, newer cell-based approaches such as GUIDE-seq, BLISS, and DISCOVER-seq (121-123) can be used to test off-target editing in a genome-wide unbiased manner. GUIDE-seq, for example, tags DSBs created by genome editors with small oligonucleotides (123).

The PCR-amplified genomic sites are then sequenced to trace the locus in the genome. While GUIDE-seq has been widely used in cultured cells, it would be difficult to adapt this approach to *in vivo* genome editing because it involves oligonucleotide transfection. Reasonable platforms to evaluate genome editing in patient cells are needed regardless of whether cell-based methods in this group are used. Third, unbiased cell-free *in vitro* assays including Digenome-seq, SITE-seq, and CIRCLE-seq have recently been developed (124-126).

To detect genome-wide CRISPR/Cas9 action, these assays use cell-free genomic DNA isolated from target cells or tissues. They should prevent drawbacks associated with culture conditions and modification of living cells because genome editing is conducted in a cell-free *in vitro* environment using isolated genomic DNA in these assays. Cell-free methods have such a high sensitivity compared to cell-based methods that they can identify even unusual off-target sites. This benefit is critical in the clinical implementation of therapeutic genome editing, where unusual off-target mutations can trigger lethal phenotypes. One research found that by coupling cell-free CIRCLE-seq with amplicon sequencing, almost all off-target sites caused by *in vivo* genome editing can be identified (68). There are two steps to this method: After *in vivo* genome editing, CIRCLE-seq was used to recognize off-target candidates using extracted genomic DNA (*in vitro* discovery step), and then targeted amplicon sequencing against these candidates was performed in mouse liver samples (*in vivo* confirmation step). Since it is a noninvasive approach that can reflect each patient's genetic history, this technique may be used for therapeutic genome editing in patients.

In terms of attempts to minimize off-target effects, it has been shown that using well-designed gRNAs is important for achieving low off-target effects. When a "promiscuous" gRNA was used against Pcsk9, for example, 19 off-target mutations were detected in the mouse liver, while no

off-target mutations were detected when a well-designed gRNA was used (68). Other than gRNA sequences, a variety of attempts have been made to increase editing accuracy, including approaches that use shorter gRNAs (115,119,120), chemically adapted gRNAs (127), Cas9 nickase variants that cause two single-strand breaks instead of DSBs (128,129), and engineered new Cas9 variants (130-134). Although some of these non-traditional approaches seem promising, even higher fidelity Cas9 variants have lower editing performance, and delivery methods for in vivo therapeutic genome editing must be optimized.

3.4. Efficient and tissue-specific genome editor distribution

Aside from the challenges inside genome editors, delivering genome editors to target tissues and cells is a big obstacle for clinical application (1,52,88). Therapeutic genome editing, including on-target editing and off-target mutagenesis, necessitates the effective and precise distribution of genome editors to the target tissues. In vivo delivery methods for most gene therapies currently depend on AAV vectors, which have been licensed by the FDA (1). Despite the fact that existing AAV systems have drawbacks such as cargo size and immunogenicity, they are highly efficient at delivering to a range of tissue types, including the eye, brain, liver, and muscle (135,136). The viral delivery system with AAV9 has already been used in clinical trials of cardiac gene therapies in the cardiovascular region (137).

For CRISPR/Cas9-based genome editing, all Cas9 and gRNAs must be administered to the target tissues, either separately or together. A repair template is also needed for HDR-mediated gene correction. To accomplish the desired genome editing, selecting the right expression system and distribution mechanism is crucial. Early research using methods such as plasmids or viruses to deliver the Cas9 and gRNA coding sequences (1-3,88). While these DNA-delivery approaches have been used in several trials, both in vitro and in vivo, there are several possible drawbacks to consider, such as strong off-target effects due to prolonged Cas9 expression, the need for active promoters in the target cells, the chance of DNA absorption into the genome, and so on. Methods for delivering Cas9 as mRNA or protein to target cells have been established to prevent these complications (52,87,88). Current experiments (138) have favored the use of a ribonucleoprotein (RNP), which is a Cas9 protein in complex with a gRNA. RNPs will function directly after transmission because they don't need Cas9 transcription and have less off-target effects because Cas9 expression isn't prolonged. Lipofection or electroporation in vitro may be used to deliver RNPs to target cells. Many expression mechanisms and distribution methods designed for in vitro platforms can be used for ex vivo therapeutic applications, such as blood cell editing (1,52,88). RNPs with electroporation are the best tool for achieving transient expression of genome editors currently available. RNPs may also be administered using chemical conjugation or engineered cell-penetrating peptides. However, this form of application is restricted to the cardiovascular field (1,52,88).

The distribution options for in vivo applications are currently limited to viral vectors (1,52,88). Because of their low immunogenic capacity, decreased genome integration, and wide range of serotype specificity, AAV vectors are preferred (65,135,136). In a number of tissues, including the eye, brain, liver, and muscle, each AAV serotype has high efficacy. AAV9 has also been used in clinical trials of cardiac gene therapy in the cardiovascular region (137). AAV vectors, on the other hand, have a number of drawbacks. First, since the packaging size is limited (up to 4.5 kb except the inverted terminal repeats), delivering Cas9 and gRNAs in a single vector is difficult. SpCas9, the most widely used Cas9 version, is 4.2 kb in length, leaving no space for gRNAs and speech control components. AAV will benefit from smaller Cas9 orthologs (SaCas9, CjCas9, and NmeCas9) (65, 139-142). There are ongoing attempts to find natural Cas proteins or engineer Cas variants that are smaller and more reliable. CasX, a recently discovered RNA-guided nuclease, is smaller (1000 aa) than Cas9 and may allow for more AAV-mediated delivery (143). Second, AAV-mediated delivery could result in Cas9 expression that is persistent, potentially causing genomic instability and DNA damage (135,136). Third, since the patient can develop immunity to the AAV serotype, a one-shot treatment is needed for AAV delivery (135,136). Furthermore, previous to the administration of AAV vectors, a large proportion of patients could have been naturally exposed to AAVs and already immunized (135).

While nanoparticle-based delivery methods for Cas9 mRNA or RNPs for in vivo application have not been extensively tested compared to viral vectors, several studies have shown their potential (144,145). It's still necessary to achieve tissue-type or cell-type specificity, minimize nanoparticle component toxicity, and prevent immunogenicity of Cas9 proteins (50–80 percent have been confirmed to be immunized to SpCas9 and SaCas9), just as it is with viral vectors (146).

3.5. Ethical considerations

Despite genome editing's enormous therapeutic potential, its ease of use and powerful results have raised significant and growing ethical questions (1-4,50). A big scandal in November 2018 regarding the world's first "CRISPRed infants" exposed some of the significant ethical questions around the proposed use of human genome editing (147,148). Since the ethical problems surrounding human genome editing are complex and contentious, a detailed overview in this study is impossible. Here's a quick rundown of some key points.

The heritability of genome editing is one of the most serious issues (1-4 ,50). Genome editing of embryos or germline cells to cure familial hereditary disorders will theoretically be more effective than genome editing in vivo after birth. This technique has the potential to permanently eradicate genetic defects, including in offspring. Genome editing of embryos for the treatment of genetic abnormalities has been shown in mouse models to result in offspring carrying the modified gene (81,149). Genome editing of human embryos has already been studied and shown to be possible (150,151). However, there has been no agreement or consensus about the consequences of artificially introduced genetic

modifications in embryos and germline cells that can be passed down to future generations.

Another crucial question is what diseases or traits should be accepted as genome editing targets (1-4, 50). It will be widely accepted to treat unusual genetic defects that cause serious lethal diseases. There will be few objections to using gene editing to prevent diseases in people with elevated risk factors (e.g., targeting PCSK9 for hereditary hyperlipidemia). However, gene editing for the prevention of very common diseases or for the "enhancement" of a trait (e.g., height, memory, learning, physical appearance, etc.) may spark debate. The ethical acceptability of genome editing in a specific case is determined by social expectations and the medical history of each patient, and these questions remain beyond the scope of scientific debate. To regulate these matters, appropriate international ethical standards and rules are needed (148, 154-215).

IV. Concluding remarks

Genome editing tools, especially CRISPR/Cas9 systems, have emerged as a powerful and promising technology for both in vitro and in vivo genomic manipulation. While genome editing has been used as a research method to study disease pathogenesis in the cardiovascular field, practical clinical use of therapeutic genome editing is still limited. PCSK9 is one of the most promising candidates for therapeutic genome editing in the liver, and it has been extensively investigated for risk reduction in cardiovascular diseases. Despite this, treating the heart remains difficult due to the inefficiency of existing genome editing methods and delivery mechanisms in the heart. Since therapeutic genome editing is still in its early stages but is steadily advancing, we can anticipate a steady stream of new editing methods targeting broader use. To use such innovative techniques for clinical purposes, efficient and secure delivery mechanisms would need to be created.

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